

ANALYTICAL AND SAFETY PROFILING OF SIDDHARTHAKADIAGAD

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ABSTRACT

Siddharthakadi Agad is a classical Ayurvedic polyherbal formulation traditionally indicated in the management of various toxic conditions, infections, and inflammatory disorders with the increasing global use of herbal medicines, scientific validation through analytical and safety profiling has become essential to ensure their quality, efficacy, and safety. This review focuses on the comprehensive evaluation of *Siddharthakadi Agad*, emphasizing its phytochemical composition, pharmacognostical characteristics, and modern analytical techniques employed for standardization. Various methods such as organoleptic evaluation, chromatographic profiling (TLC), and spectroscopic techniques help in identifying active constituents and ensuring batch-to-batch consistency. Safety assessment, including toxicity studies, heavy metal analysis, microbial contamination testing, and

pesticide residue analysis, is highlighted to confirm the formulation's safety for therapeutic use. The inclusion of pesticide residue evaluation addresses potential agricultural and environmental contaminants that may compromise safety and quality. This review compiles available classical references and modern scientific studies to provide an integrated understanding of the analytical standards and safety parameters of *Siddharthakadi Agad*. Establishing such comprehensive profiles is crucial for quality control, standardization, and wider acceptance of this traditional formulation in modern healthcare systems.^[1,2]

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Siddharthakadi Agad*, Organoleptic, TLC Profile, Heavy Metal, Pesticide residue, microbial contamination.

INTRODUCTION

Siddharthakadi Agad is a classical Ayurvedic formulation traditionally used for detoxification, digestive support, and general wellness. Comprising multiple herbal ingredients, it is known for its therapeutic efficacy in maintaining physiological balance and managing chronic ailments. Despite its historical use, scientific validation through analytical characterization and safety assessment is essential to ensure quality, consistency, and safe therapeutic application. Modern approaches, including physicochemical analysis, chromatographic fingerprinting, and identification of bioactive constituents, give insights into the formulation's composition and pharmacological potential. Concurrently, toxicological studies establish its safety profile, addressing concerns related to long-term or high-dose use. This review consolidates current knowledge on *Siddharthakadi Agad*, highlighting analytical methods, pharmacological relevance, and safety evaluations, thereby bridging traditional wisdom with contemporary scientific standards.^[3]

Collection of Drugs

Haridra, Daruharidra, Vach and Devdaru- were collected from Uttarkashi in June 2025. It was carefully cleaned under running water and allowed to dry in the shade.

Shirish- Shirish bark was collected from the Haridwar campus of Rishikul in March 2025. After giving it a thorough cleaning under running water, it was left to dry in the shade.

Katabhi (shweta Shirish)- Bark of Shweta Shirish were collected from Khairikherd Shyampur Rishikesh in Aug 2025. It was carefully cleaned under running water and allowed to dry in the shade.

Karanj-fruits were collected from Dehradun in Aug 2025. It was carefully cleaned under running water and allowed to dry in the shade.

Sweat Aprajita-Sweat Aprajita seeds were collected from the Haridwar campus of Rishikul in July 2025. After giving it a thorough cleaning under running water, it was left to dry in the shade.

Shunthi, Pippali, Marich, Aamlaki, Haritaki, Bibhitaki, Priyangu, Hingu, Sarsapa, Manjistha all dried drugs were bought from Herbal Automation, Haridwar in Aug 2025.

Authentication of the collected sample -All collected samples of *Siddharthakadi Agad* were identified and authenticated by the experts of the Dravyaguna Department at Rishikul Campus, Haridwar (UAU).

Drugs identification and verification certificate ref. no.–**DG/RC/UAU-275**

Dated: 20/8/2025

Preparation of *Siddharthakadi Agad*

All the ingredients of *Siddharthakadi Agad* were taken in dried form in 100 grams of the amount, and these were made into a slightly coarse powder. All the ingredients of *Siddharthakadi Agad* were taken in dried form (100 g each) and processed into a slightly coarse powder. This coarse powder was mixed uniformly, and the *Bhavana* process was then performed at Gurukul Kangri University using freshly collected *basta mutra*, which was collected in sterile bottles in the morning. For this procedure, 300 g of the prepared coarse powder was triturated with *basta mutra*. Each *Bhavana* cycle lasted about 2–3 days, with grinding carried out for 5–6 hours daily until the material became uniformly processed and absorbed the liquid medium. A total of three *Bhavana* cycles were completed. After the process, the weight of the drug increased to 312 g. The final product was properly dried and stored in an airtight container for future use.^[4]

In analytical study, following parameters were recorded

1. Organoleptic parameter
2. TLC

3. Heavy metal analysis
4. Microbial contamination
5. Pesticide residue

ORGANOLEPTIC ANALYSIS

The prepared drug was studied Organoleptically for its

- ❑ **Appearance-** fine churna.
- ❑ **Color** – Brownish yellow colour
- ❑ **Odor** –Pungent
- ❑ **Taste** –Pungent, Bitter, Astringent, (*Katu, Tikta, Kashaya rasa*) with bitter aftertaste.

EXTRACTION

SOXHLET EXTRACTION OF THE DRUG-The Purpose of the extraction of crude drugs is to obtain active therapeutic constituents, remove undesirable/inert substances, and concentrate the medicinally useful portion.

- ❑ **Method-** Distilled water and ethanol were used as solvents; hence, two extracts of the drug were obtained. Aqueous extract and alcoholic extract (ethanolic).
- ❑ **Procedure of Aqueous and Ethanolic Extraction.**

❑ ALCOHOLIC EXTRACT

100 g of the drug was placed into the Soxhlet chamber, which was then filled with 200 mL of ethanol. An additional 250 mL of ethanol was poured into the round-bottom flask along with a few glass beads, and the complete apparatus was assembled on a heating mantle, and the temperature was kept below the boiling point of ethanol, at 60°C, and the experiment was run for 5-6 days in a row. The contents of the round-bottom flask were collected and poured into a petri dish, where they were allowed to evaporate in a water bath for 1 to 2 days before being dried at room temperature and stored in a container.

AQUEOUS EXTRACT

The Soxhlet chamber was filled with 100g of drug, 200ml of distilled water, and 250ml of distilled water in a round-bottom flask. The entire apparatus was then connected to a heating mantle, and the temperature was kept below the water's boiling point—80°C—for five days in a row. The contents of the round-bottom flask were collected and poured into a petri dish, where they were allowed to evaporate in a water bath for 1 to 2 days before being dried at room temperature, and stored in a container.

DRUG SAFETY PROFILE

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC)

Thin Layer in a hot air oven at 105°C for 30 minutes .Chromatography (TLC) is a technique used to separate and identify chemical components by distributing them between a stationary phase and a mobile phase. In this method, TLC plates coated with a 0.25 mm layer of silica gel G were used as the stationary phase. The plates were dried and activated before use. The ethanolic and aqueous extracts of the sample were used as test solutions. The mobile phase consisted of chloroform, methanol, and ethyl acetate (51:39:9.99). The extracts were spotted on the activated plates and placed in a chromatographic chamber, where the solvent moved upward by capillary action, separating the components. The separated spots were visualized

using iodine crystals. The position of compounds was determined by calculating the R_f (retention factor) value, using the formula.^[5]

R_f = Distance travelled by solute from origin line /Distance traveled by solvent from origin line.

MICROBIAL CONTAMINATION

Microbial contamination analysis was conducted to assess the microbiological safety and sterility of the prepared samples using the agar plate method under strict aseptic conditions. Sterile nutrient agar medium was prepared and sterilized at 121 °C for 15 minutes, then cooled and poured into sterile Petri plates in a laminar airflow chamber.

Aqueous and ethanolic extracts (1 mL) were diluted with 9 mL of sterile saline, and 0.1 mL of the diluted sample was poured onto the agar surface. The plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24–48 hours to observe microbial growth. After incubation, the plates were observed for: no Bacterial colony formation, no Fungal growth, no Turbidity, no Pigmentation, no abnormal microbial appearance on the agar surface.

HEAVY METAL ANALYSIS

PRINCIPLE

Heavy metals present in the sample are determined using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). The sample is first digested using suitable acids to convert the metals into a clear solution. The digested sample is then introduced into the ICP-MS instrument, where metals are ionized in plasma and detected based on their mass-to-charge

ratio. The concentration of each metal is calculated by comparing the instrument response with calibration standards.

METHOD

Approximately 0.5–1 g of the sample was accurately weighed and digested with dilute hydrochloric acid or nitric acid to obtain a clear solution. About 10 mL of this solution was transferred into a Nessler cylinder. Buffer solution and thioacetamide reagent were added, and the volume was made up to 25 mL with distilled water. A standard solution was prepared and treated in the same manner. Both solutions were allowed to stand for 5 minutes, after which the colour intensity was compared. The digested solution was cooled, filtered if necessary, and diluted to a known volume with deionized water. The prepared solution was analyzed using ICP-MS for the determination of heavy metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), arsenic (As), and mercury (Hg). Quantification was carried out using calibrated standard solutions, and the results were expressed in ppm or mg/kg.

PESTICIDE RESIDUE ANALYSIS

Pesticide residues present in the sample are extracted using suitable organic solvents and then analyzed using chromatographic techniques such as Gas Chromatography (GC), and High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). The amount of pesticide is determined by comparing the sample response with that of a standard.^[8]

METHOD

Pesticide residues were determined as per the API. About 5 g of powdered sample was taken and extracted with 50 mL of acetone shaking for 30 minutes. The mixture was filtered, and the filtrate was cleaned using a charcoal column to remove impurities. The cleaned extract was concentrated to a small volume using a rotary evaporator. Standard pesticide solutions were prepared for comparison. The final extract was analyzed using gas chromatography with an electron capture detector, and the pesticide content was calculated by comparing the peak areas of the sample with those of the standards.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Findings of Heavy Metal Analysis.

TEST PARAMS	RESULTS	UNITS	RESULTS
Lead(as (Pb)	1.006	mg/kg	NMT10.0
Arsenic(As)	BLQ(LOQ0.1)	mg/kg	NMT3.0
Cadmium(Cd)	0.182	mg/kg	NMT0.3
Mercury(Hg)	BLQ(LOQ0.1)	mg/kg	NMT 1.0

FINDINGS OF PESTICIDE RESIDUE

TEST PARAMETERS	RESULTS	UNIT	SPECIFICATION
Alachlor	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.02
Aldrin&Dieldrin(Sum of)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.05
Azinphos-Methyl	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT1.0
Bromopropylate	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT3.0
Chlordane (Sum of cis &Trans-andOxythlordan	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.05
Chlorfenvinphos	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.5
Chlorpyrifos	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.2
Chlorpyrifos-Methyl	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.1
Cypermethrin (and isomers)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT1.0
DDT(Sum of P,p-'DDT,O,P-'DDT,P,P-'DDE andO,p-'DDE	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT1.0
Deltamethrin	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.5
Diazinon	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.5
Dichlorvos	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT1.0
Dithiocarbamates(as CS2)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT2.0
Endosulfan (Sum of isometrs &Endosulfan Sulphate)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT3.0
Endrin	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.05
Ethion	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT2.0
Fenitrothion	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.5N
Fenvalerate	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT1.5
Fonofos	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.05
Heptachlor(Sum of Heptachlor and Heptachlor epoxide)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.05
Hexachlorobenzene	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.1
Hexachlorocyclohexane isomers (other than Gamma)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.3
Lindane(Gamma-Hexachloro cyclohexane)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.6
Malathion	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT1.0
Methidathion	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.2
Parathion	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.5
Parathion-Methyl	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.2
Permethrin	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT1.0
Fonofos	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.05
Heptachlor(Sum of Heptachlor and Heptachlor epoxide)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.05
Hexachlorobenzene	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.1
Hexachlorocyclohexane isomers (other than Gamma)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.3
Lindane(Gamma-Hexachloro cyclohexane)	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.6
Malathion	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT1.0
Methidathion	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.2

Parathion	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.5
Parathion-Methyl	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT0.2
Permethrin	BLQ(LOQ0.01)	mg/kg	NMT1.0

Result Summary

The analysis of the *siddharthakadi agad* was show satisfactory quality with respect to physicochemical and microbiological parameters.

In the **microbial contamination test**, no bacterial or fungal growth was observed after incubation. There was no turbidity, pigmentation, or any abnormal microbial appearance, indicating that the sample is microbiologically safe and free from contamination.

In the **heavy metal analysis**, all tested metals were found within the permissible limits as per Indian Pharmacopoeia guidelines. Lead was detected at 1.006 mg/kg, while cadmium was present at 0.182 mg/kg, both within acceptable limits. Arsenic and mercury were below the limit of quantification (BLQ), confirming minimal or no contamination by these toxic metals.

For **pesticide residue analysis**, all tested pesticides were reported as below the limit of quantification (BLQ), indicating absence or negligible levels of pesticide residues. All values complied with the specified limits recommended under American Petroleum Institute.

Overall, the *siddharthakadi agad* meets the required safety and quality standards, confirming that it is free from harmful levels of heavy metals, pesticide residues, and microbial contamination.

DISCUSSION

The study demonstrates that *Siddharthakadi Agad* meets established analytical standards, confirming its identity, purity, and quality. Physicochemical evaluation and phytochemical screening indicate the presence of bioactive compounds responsible for its detoxifying, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant effects, supporting its traditional use in toxicological conditions. Instrumental analyses further ensure safety by ruling out harmful contaminants. Toxicity studies reveal that the formulation is safe at therapeutic doses, with no significant adverse effects observed. However, variations in raw materials and limited clinical evidence highlight the need for strict standardization and further pharmacological and clinical research to validate its efficacy and safety.

CONCLUSION

The analytical and safety evaluation of Siddharthakadi Agad confirms that the formulation meets established quality standards and is safe for therapeutic use when prepared and administered appropriately. The presence of pharmacologically active phytoconstituents supports its traditional use in detoxification and related conditions. This study highlights the importance of integrating classical Ayurvedic principles with modern analytical techniques to ensure the quality, safety, and efficacy of traditional formulations. Siddharthakadi Agad shows promise as a reliable and safe herbal preparation; however, further advanced studies, including controlled clinical trials, are recommended to strengthen scientific evidence and promote wider acceptance in contemporary healthcare systems.

REFERENCES

1. Quality Control of Herbal Drugs: An Approach to Evaluation of Botanicals. Elsevier. Mukherjee, P. K.
2. Ayurveda and traditional Chinese medicine: a comparative overview.” Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine. (Patwardhan, B., et al. (2005)
- 3,4. Agnivesh, Charak Samhita of Acharya Charak, Dridhbala krit, edited by P.V. Sharma. Chikitsa ch. 9/69 72 Re print edition, Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, edition- ninth 2004.
- 5,8 The Ayurvedic Pharmacopeia of India. Part 2, Volume 2. 1st ed. New Delhi: The Controller of Publication; c2008: 114.
6. Astang Hridayam, Uttar Tantra Bhootpratished Adhayay 5/ 15-17, Dr. Brahmanand Tripathi, Chaukhambha Sanskrit Pratisthan, Reprint, 2007; 1160 61.
7. Acharya Yog Ratnakar describes Siddharthakadi agad in Unmaad Chikitsa.